

A STUDY ON SELF-EFFICACY AMONG B.Ed STUDENTS OF KAMRUP (METRO) AND KAMRUP DISTRICTS OF ASSAM

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Abstract

Self-efficacy refers to a person's beliefs about his own capability of doing a task by his own. Self-efficacy of pre-service teachers' is important as it helps them to become an effective teacher. So, through their pre-service training program, they must have to acquire some kinds of knowledge and skills as well as self-efficacy to the extent that helps them to manage classroom activities effectively, motivate students, to plan their teaching with proper strategy, etc. The purpose of the present study is to explore Self-efficacy among B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam, India. The researchers have used Simple Random Sampling Technique to select 560 B.Ed students as a sample for the present study. Descriptive Survey Method is adopted by the researchers. Self-efficacy Scale (SES) developed and standardized by Dr.Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain (2014) is adapted by the researchers to collect data. The findings revealed that there is significant difference among B.Ed students according to their gender and stream (Science and Arts) but locality wise no such difference is found.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, B.Ed Students, Kamrup, Metro.

INTRODUCTION

According to the famous psychologist Albert Bandura, self-efficacy is an individual's belief in his or her capacity to execute behaviour necessary to produce specific performance attainments (Bandura, 1977, 1989, 1997).

A person with a high self-efficacy can face every challenge with courage and confidence because they possess the belief that they can handle it, they have that much of ability to control it. While the person with low self-efficacy takes challenges in a negative way and try to avoid it. They possess lack of faith on their own abilities to face the challenge.

Teacher education refers to that type of education which involves various programs, procedures, etc., designed to prepare an individual as an effective teacher equipped with knowledge, skills, competencies, attitude, and behaviour they need to perform their task effectively in classroom as well as in society. Two kinds of teacher education programmes are there: pre-service teacher education programme and in-service teacher education programme. B.Ed program belongs to pre-service teacher education.

The National Council for Teacher Education defined Teacher Education as "A programme of education, research and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education level".

The present Teacher Training Institutions like College of Teacher Education (CTE), District Institute of Education and Training (DIET), etc., are trying hard to inculcate

different kinds of skills, like Teaching skills, Pedagogical skills, Professional skills among Teacher trainees such that their knowledge base can become more stronger and this will suppose to increase their self-efficacy accordingly. B.Ed trainees are thus also tried to equip with different kinds of skills along with knowledge about Philosophy, Psychology and Sociology such that they can develop confidence and ability related to teaching. In such way they can become very effective teachers in near future.

The present study is trying to explore the self-efficacy of the B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam.

Objectives of The Present Study: The objectives of the present study include:

- (1) To find out the level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam.
- (2) To find out the level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) district of Assam.
- (3) To find out the level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed Students of Kamrup district of Assam.
- (4) To compare the level of Self-Efficacy of B.Ed students with respect to their
 - (a) Gender
 - (b) Stream of study
- (5) To compare the level of Self-Efficacy of B.Ed students among Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam.

Research Questions and Hypotheses:

In order to accomplish the above cited objectives, the following research questions and hypotheses were formulated:

Research questions:

1. What is the level of self-efficacy among B.Ed students in Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam?
2. What is the level of self-efficacy among B.Ed students in Kamrup (Metro) district of Assam?
3. What is the level of self-efficacy among B.Ed students in Kamrup district of Assam?
4. (a) Is there a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy between male and female B.Ed students?
(b) Is there a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy among B.Ed students from different streams of study (e.g., Arts, Science, Commerce)?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy among B.Ed students from Kamrup (Metro) district and Kamrup district of Assam?

Research Hypothesis:

H1: There is no significant difference among boys and girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their Self-efficacy is concerned.

H2: There is no significant difference among Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their Self-efficacy is concerned.

H3: There is no significant difference among B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their Self-efficacy is concerned.

Research Method Used:

Keeping in view the nature and objectives of the study, the researcher has adopted Descriptive Survey Method for the proposed study.

Population and Sample:

Population: The population of the present study comprises of all the B.Ed students studying in different Government and Private Teacher Training Institutes, DIET, Universities in Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam that are offering B.Ed courses. There are 1(one) DIET, 1(one) University, 1 Govt B.Ed and 12 private B.Ed Colleges in Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam. Overall, there are 15 institutions with 1300 students that offer B.Ed courses in Kamrup(Metro) and Kamrup District, Assam.

Sample: For the proposed study, the researchers have adopted Simple Random Sampling Technique for selecting the sample. The sample is consisting of 560 B.Ed trainees studying in different Private B.Ed institutions affiliated to Gauhati University of both Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam.

Tools Used In the Study:

In order to achieve the objectives, the following tools were selected for the proposed study:

- Self-efficacy Scale (SES) developed and standardized by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain (2014) and adopted by the researchers themselves.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Level of Self-Efficacy among B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam

In order to determine the level of self-efficacy of B.Ed students, the researchers had administered the Self-efficacy Scale (SES) developed and standardized by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain (2014) and adopted by the researchers on 560 B.Ed students and then calculated Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis.

Table 1: Level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

Area	Mean	Median	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
SE (As a whole)	72.29	76.15	9.18	-1.26	0.257
Self-confidence	18.62	18.36	12.58	0.062	0.297
Efficacy expectation	19.11	19.06	3.29	0.046	0.302
Positive attitude	19.18	19.04	2.80	0.15	0.311
Outcome expectation	19.57	19.68	2.75	-0.128	0.313

The above table-1 shows that the Mean, Median and SD are 72.29, 76.15 and 9.18 respectively. The distribution of Self-efficacy scores of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is negatively skewed or skewed towards the left; i.e., scores are massed at the higher end (the right end) of the scale and are spread out gradually towards the low end (the left end).

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is 0.257 which is less than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is leptokurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is positively skewed, i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards high end (the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.62, 18.36 and 12.58 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is 0.297 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of the scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficiency expectation) scores of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is positively skewed, i.e., scores are

massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards high end (the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.11, 19.06 and 3.29 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficiency expectation) of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is 0.302 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of the scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is positively skewed, i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards high end (the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.18, 19.04 and 2.80 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is 0.311 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of the scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is negatively skewed, i.e., scores are massed at the higher end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards low end (the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.57, 19.68 and 2.75 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam is 0.313 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of the scores is platykurtic.

Figure 1: Level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam

Above Figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores of the B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam in the Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that 260 students scored in the range 70-79 and only 2 students scored below the range 50-59. Moreover one student scored 100.

The researchers also attempted to categorise the B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 2: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

Categories	Descriptions	Range of Scores				Total Students
		Female	No of Students	Male	No of Students	
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	51	85 and above	27	78
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	147	74 to 84	133	280
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	82	73 or less	120	202

Level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) district of Assam:

In order to determine the level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students of Assam, the researchers had administered the Self-efficacy scale on 280 students of Kamrup (Metro) district. The researchers then calculated the Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. The following table shows the level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students of Assam.

Table 3: Level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed Students:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-efficacy (Full scale)	76.95	77.03	7.88	-0.030	0.265
Self-confidence	18.77	18.55	3.25	0.203	0.305
Efficacy expectation	19.27	19.24	3.13	0.029	0.312
Positive attitude	19.19	19.14	2.91	0.051	0.311
Outcome expectation	20.07	20.38	2.61	-0.356	0.302

From the above table-3 it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 76.95, 77.03 and 7.88 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is 0.265 which is slightly greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic. The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.77, 18.55 and

3.25 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is 0.305 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.27, 19.24 and 3.13 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is 0.312 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.19, 19.14 and 2.91 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is 0.311 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 20.07, 20.38 and 2.61 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students is 0.302 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 2: Level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students of Assam

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores obtained by the Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students of Assam in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that total 73 Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students secured score in the range 75-79, while 2 students secured score in the range 55-59 and only 1 scored 100.

The researchers also attempted to categorise the Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the Kamrup (Metro) students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 4: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup (Metro) B.Ed Students of Assam:

Categories	Descriptions	Range of Scores				Total Students
		Female	No of Students	Male	No of Students	
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	29	85 and above	15	44
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	69	74 to 84	70	139
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	42	73 or less	55	97

Level of Self-efficacy among B.Ed students of Kamrup district of Assam:

In order to determine the level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup B.Ed students of Assam, the researchers had administered the Self-efficacy scale on 280 students of Kamrup district. The researchers then calculated the Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. The following table shows the level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup B.Ed students of Assam.

Table 5: Level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup District of Assam:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-efficacy (Full scale)	75.71	75.80	7.93	-0.034	0.248
Self-confidence	18.46	18.20	2.87	0.272	0.288
Efficacy expectation	18.95	18.89	2.94	0.061	0.309
Positive attitude	19.16	18.94	2.68	0.246	0.309
Outcome expectation	19.07	18.88	2.8	0.204	0.431

From the above table it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Kamrup B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 75.71, 75.80 and 7.93 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Kamrup B.Ed students is 0.248 which is less than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is leptokurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Kamrup B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the

scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.46, 18.20 and 2.87 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Kamrup B.Ed students is 0.288 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Kamrup B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.95, 18.89 and 2.94 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) of Kamrup B.Ed students is 0.309 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Kamrup B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.16, 18.94 and 2.68 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Kamrup B.Ed students is 0.309 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Kamrup B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.07, 18.88 and 2.8 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Kamrup B.Ed students is 0.431 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 3: Level of Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup District of Assam

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores obtained by the Kamrup B.Ed students in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that total 138 Kamrup B.Ed students secured scores in the range 70-79, and 2 students secured score below the range 50-59 and only 4 students secured score in between 90-99.

The researchers also attempted to categorise the Kamrup B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the Kamrup students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 6: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Kamrup B.Ed Students of Assam:

Categories	Descriptions	Range of Scores				Total Students
		Female	No of Students	Male	No of Students	
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	22	85 and above	12	34
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	78	74 to 84	63	141
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	40	73 or less	65	105

Level of Self-efficacy among Boys B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

In order to determine the level of self-efficacy of boys, the researchers have administered the Self-efficacy Scale on 280 boys. The researcher had calculated Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis.

Table 7: Level of Self-efficacy among Boys B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-efficacy (Full scale)	75.41	75.32	6.92	0.039	0.288
Self-confidence	18.5	18.13	2.65	0.419	0.279
Efficacy expectation	18.91	18.71	2.93	0.204	0.307
Positive attitude	19.04	18.83	2.64	0.239	0.307
Outcome expectation	19.11	18.84	2.58	0.314	0.307

From the above table-7 it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Boys B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 75.41, 75.32 and 6.92 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Boys B.Ed students is 0.288 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Boys B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the

scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.5, 18.13 and 2.65 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Boys B.Ed students is 0.279 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Boys B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.91, 18.71 and 2.93 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy-expectation) of Boys B.Ed students is 0.307 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Boys B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.04, 18.83 and 2.64 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Boys B.Ed students is 0.307 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Boys B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.11, 18.84 and 2.58 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Boys B.Ed students is 0.307 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 4: Level of Self-efficacy of Boys (Full Scale)

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores of the Boys B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that total 73 boys students scored in between 75 to 79 and 9 boys scored in the range 60-64 while only 1 boy scored in the range 95-99.

The researchers also attempted to categorize the Boys B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the Boys B.Ed students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 8: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Boys B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

Categories	Description	Range of Scores	
		Male	No of Students
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	27
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	133
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	120

Level of Self-efficacy of Girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

In order to determine the level of self-efficacy of girls, the researchers have administered the Self-efficacy Scale on 280 girls. The researchers had calculated Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. The following Table shows the level of Self-efficacy of Girls of B.Ed students of kmarup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam.

Table 9: Level of Self-efficacy of Girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-efficacy (Full scale)	77.46	77.53	8.83	-0.024	0.273
Self-confidence	18.73	18.38	3.43	0.306	0.357
Efficacy expectation	19.30	19.46	3.13	-0.153	0.313
Positive attitude	19.29	19.28	2.95	0.010	0.312
Outcome expectation	20.04	20.43	2.85	-0.411	0.300

From the above table-9 it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Girls B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 77.46, 77.53 and 8.83 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Girls B.Ed students is 0.273 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Girls B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the

scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.73, 18.38 and 3.43 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Girls B.Ed students is 0.357 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Girls B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.30, 19.46 and 3.13 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy-expectation) of Girls B.Ed students is 0.313 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Girls B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.29, 19.28 and 2.95 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Girls B.Ed students is 0.312 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Girls B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 20.04, 20.43 and 2.85 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Girls B.Ed students is 0.3 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 5: Level of Self-efficacy of Girls B.Ed students (Full Scale)

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores of the Girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that total 122 girls students out of 280 girls students secured score in the range 70-79, while only 5 girls students secured score below the range 60-69 and only 1 girl student secured 100.

The researcher also attempted to categorise the Girls B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the Girls B.Ed students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 10: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Girls B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

Categories	Description	Range of Scores	
		Female	No of Students
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	51
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	147
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	82

Comparison of Self-Efficacy between Boys and Girls B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam

In order to compare SELF-EFFICACY of Boys and Girls, t-test is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between boys and girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Table 11: Comparison of SELF-EFFICACY between boys and girls B.Ed students:

Gender	N	Mean	SED	df	t	Significance
Boys	280	75.41	0.67	558	3.06	Significant at 0.05 level
Girls	280	77.46				

The above table-11 shows that the calculated value of 't' for 558 df is 3.06, which is greater than the tabulated value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between boys and girls B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned" is rejected at 0.05 level. It means that there is a significant difference between Boys and Girls B.Ed students as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Level of Self-efficacy of Science background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

In order to determine the level of Self-efficacy of Science background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam, the researchers had administered the Self-efficacy scale on 229 students who are from Science background. The researchers then calculated the Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. The

following table shows the level of Self-efficacy of Science background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam.

Table12: Level of Self-efficacy of Science Background B.Ed Students:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
As a whole	78.66	78.75	7.45	-0.036	0.247
Self-confidence	19.09	19.07	3.23	0.019	0.311
Efficacy expectation	19.71	20.05	3.08	-0.331	0.309
Positive Attitude	19.75	19.93	2.62	-0.206	0.310
Outcome expectation	19.97	20.28	2.75	-0.338	0.304

From the above table-12 it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Science background B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 78.66, 78.75 and 7.45 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Science background B.Ed students is 0.247 which is less than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is leptokurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Science background B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.09, 19.07 and 3.23 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Science background B.Ed students is 0.311 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Science background B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.71, 20.05 and 3.08 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) of Science background B.Ed students is 0.309 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Science background B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.75, 19.93 and 2.62 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Science background B.Ed students is 0.310 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Science background B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.97, 20.28 and 2.75 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Science background B.Ed students is 0.304 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 6: Level of Self-efficacy of Science Background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores obtained by the Science background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that total 63 Science background B.Ed students secured scores in between 75-79 and only 1 student secured score in between 45-49 while 1 scored 100.

The researchers also attempted to categorize the Science background B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by Science background B.Ed students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 13: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Science background B.Ed Students:

Categories	Descriptions	Range of Scores				Total Students
		Female	No of Students	Male	No of Students	
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	25	85 and above	20	45
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	61	74 to 84	70	131
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	28	73 or less	25	53

Level of Self-efficacy of Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

In order to determine the level of Self-efficacy of Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam, the researchers had administered the Self-efficacy scale on 331 students who are from Arts background. The researchers then calculated the Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. The following table shows the level of Self-efficacy of Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam.

Table 14: Level of Self-efficacy of Arts Background B.Ed Students:

Self-efficacy	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
As a whole	74.68	74.72	7.96	-0.015	0.233
Self-confidence	18.30	17.99	2.88	0.323	0.273
Efficacy expectation	18.69	18.48	2.94	0.214	0.299
Positive Attitude	18.78	18.51	2.86	0.283	0.301
Outcome expectation	19.29	19.19	2.72	0.110	0.312

From the above table-14 it is seen that the distribution of Self-efficacy scores of Arts background B.Ed students is negatively skewed or skewed to the left; i.e., scores are massed at the high end of the scale (the right end) and are spread out more gradually towards the low end (or the left end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 74.68, 74.72 and 7.96 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy of Arts background B.Ed students is 0.233 which is less than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is leptokurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) scores of Arts background B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.30, 17.99 and 2.88 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Self-confidence) of Arts background B.Ed students is 0.273 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) scores of Arts background B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end

(or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.69, 18.48 and 2.94 respectively. The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Efficacy expectation) of Arts background B.Ed students is 0.299 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) scores of Arts background B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 18.78, 18.51 and 2.86 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Positive attitude) of Arts background B.Ed students is 0.301 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

The distribution of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) scores of Arts background B.Ed students is positively skewed or skewed to the right; i.e., scores are massed at the low end of the scale (the left end) and are spread out more gradually towards the high end (or the right end). In this distribution, Mean, Median and SD are 19.29, 19.19 and 2.72 respectively.

The computed value of Kurtosis of Self-efficacy (Outcome expectation) of Arts background B.Ed students is 0.312 which is greater than 0.263. It indicates that the distribution of scores is platykurtic.

Figure 7: Level of Self-efficacy of Arts Background B.Ed students

The above figure shows the frequency curve indicating the scores obtained by the Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam in Self-efficacy scale. From the figure it is clear that 160 Arts background B.Ed students secured scores in the range 70-79 and only 5 students scored in between 90-99, while 1 only student scored in the range 30-39.

The researchers also attempted to categorise the Arts background B.Ed students into three (3) different categories namely, High Self-efficacy, Average Self-efficacy and Poor Self-efficacy on the basis of range of scores obtained by the Arts background B.Ed students in the Self-efficacy scale. The following Table shows the number of students under different categories:

Table 15: Category wise distribution of level of Self-efficacy of Arts background B.Ed Students:

Categories	Descriptions	Range of Scores				Total Students
		Female	No of Students	Male	No of Students	
1	High Self-efficacy	85 and above	26	85 and above	7	33
2	Average Self-efficacy	74 to 84	86	74 to 84	63	149
3	Poor Self-efficacy	73 or less	54	73 or less	95	149

Comparison of Self-Efficacy between Science and Arts Background B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

In order to compare SELF-EFFICACY between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts, t-test is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Table 16: Comparison of SELF-EFFICACY between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

Stream (Background)	N	Mean	SED	df	t	Significance
Science	229	78.66	0.66	558	6.03	Significant at 0.05 level
Arts	331	74.68				

The above table-16 shows that the calculated value of 't' for 558 df is 6.03, which is greater than the tabulated value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned" is rejected at 0.05 level.

It means that there is a significant difference between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Comparison of Self-Efficacy between B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup Districts of Assam:

In order to compare SELF-EFFICACY between B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts, t-test is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Table-17: Comparison of SELF-EFFICACY between B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam:

Locality	N	Mean	SED	df	t	Significance
Kamrup(M)	280	76.95	0.69	558	1.79	Not significant at 0.05 level
Kamrup	280	75.71				

The above table-17 shows that the calculated value of 't' for 558 df is 1.79, which is smaller than the tabulated value (1.96) at 0.05 level.

Hence the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned" is accepted at 0.05 level.

It means that there is no significant difference between Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup B.Ed students as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

CONCLUSION

The present study was an attempt to study Self-efficacy of B.Ed Students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam on the basis of Gender, Locality and Stream. The researchers studied the level of self-efficacy with the help of Self-efficacy Scale (SES) developed and standardized by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain (2014).

It can be concluded that this study revealed a clear picture of the levels of Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as well as the relationship between the variables and comparison of self-efficacy of B.Ed students with respect to Gender, Locality and Stream (Science background & Arts background).

The researchers have obtained a significant difference between Boys and Girls B.Ed students as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned. Also, no significant difference between Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup B.Ed students are found as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

Moreover it is also observed from the above study that there is a significant difference between Science and Arts background B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as far as their SELF-EFFICACY is concerned.

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